

Supporting Information

**Direct-patterning ZnO deposition
by atomic-layer additive manufacturing
using a safe and economical precursor**

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Figure S1: SEM picture of ZnO lines printed by ALAM on Si/SiO₂. (a) scanning electron micrograph of 20,40,60 and 80 passes (from left to right). (b) scanning electron micrograph of single line with 20 passes. (c) scanning electron micrograph of single line with 20 passes 5k magnification (d) scanning electron micrograph of single line with 20 passes 100k magnification

To complement the EDX measurements, XPS was used to examine the surface chemical composition of selected ZnO line features grown by ALAM at 200 °C and 250 °C on Si(100). The survey scans for the as-introduced (unspattered) surfaces show all expected signals associated with Zn and O (**Figure S2**). Additionally, the spectra contain expected signals originating from adventitious carbon with minor contribution from carboxylic carbon (**Figure S3**). Further contaminants in the form of nitrogen or silicon are not observed. While a short sputter treatment (Ar^+ , 2 min., 2 kV) helped to diminish the adventitious carbon signal, we found it to affect the ZnO material by preferential oxygen removal, which is a known phenomenon for metal oxides that can lead to misinterpretation. [7]

Figure S2: XPS survey recordings for the as introduced ZnO line surfaces of samples grown at 200 °C and 250 °C on Si(100) substrates. Core levels and Auger features are assigned based on the literature. [8]

Figure S3: C 1s core level spectra recorded for the as introduced ZnO lines grown at 200 °C and 250 °C.